

The Representation of Existentialism in the Select Novel of Saul Bellow

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Abstract

Existentialism is one of the most important themes of Saul Bellow's novels. The Adventures of Augie March is not only regarding the quest for survival but the survival of meaningful life. The whole novel deals with the life of the protagonist, Augie March. The novel is portrayed from the first person's point of view. The novel expresses the importance of existence in spite of any struggle and suffering. The novel seems to be different from those of others, but it clearly depicts the vision of the author, Saul Bellow.

Keywords: Adventures, Vision, Society, Existence, Struggle.

The Adventures of Augie March is an apt vehicle of Bellowian vision and establishes it in clear terms. Augie March, the protagonist, tells the story from his boyhood in Chicago to his wanderings in Michigan, Mexico and the African sea. In first person narrative, he keeps on telling the story of his attainment of maturity and his experiences as an import businessman in Paris. It is a picaresque novel and reflects high intellectual ideas. In this fiction, Bellow scrutinizes the working of human mind and tries to answer where the problem lies. His scrutiny establishes him as a radical thinker, who has affinity with existentialism and in some distance concerns with Buddhism.

This novel is a little different from Bellow's other novels; but it aptly demonstrates his vision. Bellow envisages human freedom from every kind of false pretensions, whether it is morality or ideality. It establishes Bellow as a writer who holds a mirror to the human beings, advocating the acceptance of their true self. In the veil of fiction, his only endeavour is to write what the truth is. Bellow's faculty to observe human nature disinterestedly makes him a free thinker. He is far from being a serious moralist. As a meticulous craftsman, he has interwoven his deep thoughts into the structure of

Augie's life. On the surface, it is in conformity with the Dickensian story of an illegitimate child; though it is a true manifesto of human predicament at a deeper level.

Bellow has stuffed the novel with several philosophical concerns. Like his other novels, in *The Adventures of Augie March*, Bellow has reflected existentialist theme. Bellow creates an aura of speculation around Augie, who is truly engaged in a struggle to choose among fantastically complicated metaphysical alternatives. The fiction also exemplifies naturalistic mode of writing. Naturalistic prose renders a human being as a product of his heredity and environment. In a naturalistic fiction, the actions of a person are determined by the compulsive instincts that he inherits together with the social and the economic forces of the family and the society, in which he is born. In this novel, Bellow shows a deep sense of environmental intrusion and of life as competitive struggle chaotically releasing and suppressing energy. Bellow portrays an urban mechanical world in which the individuality is influenced by dominant processes and the laws of social places. The character of Augie is also influenced by his unhealthy family atmosphere. His lack of moral earnestness is a counter reaction to his illegitimate birth, docile mother and despotic grandma Lausch. On a wider level the materialism induces to behave immorally instead of being sincere. Bellow has followed the tradition of picaresque novel. He has used a great number of characters and detailed action that covers the period of several years.

Bellow's other protagonists struggle in acceptance of their true self but the case is different with Augie. He has no aversion to evil or immoral behaviour as long as it is true to his instincts. In view of modern devaluation of human spirit, Augie's plea to have free existence reminds one of the Satan, the protagonist of *Paradise Lost*, book first and second. Moreover, it proves the superiority of truth over morality. Though at the same time, one cannot blame that Bellow is an immoral writer, advocating inhuman conduct. On the other hand, it is also true that Bellow has never given any sermon through his novels. It is never his motto to instruct his readers as to become good but true to oneself. And the truth of human condition is that human beings are not perfect. If one accepts one's true self, it is the most moral work that one may perform. In fact, the morality which insists one to act against one's real self can be easily discarded. Throughout his life, Bellow tried to adhere to his truth. Bellow's crusade against established morality again confirms him as an existentialist.

Morality is temporal and related to particular society. The application of moral laws differs from situation to situation. For example, to tell a lie is morally unacceptable, but if it saves someone's life, it can be accepted easily. Thus, morality is context-related and flexible. In the novel, *The Adventures of Augie March*, Augie never endeavours to be morally good. Augie, in truest sense, is a Bellovian hero, who experiments in the realm of morality. He acts according to his instincts. Through Augie's conduct Bellow tries to deconstruct the established hierarchy, which posits good at a higher level than the bad. Bellow tries to destroy all those hierarchies in the society which restrict individuals to progress further. All his heroes are victims of this internal conflict with no exception of Augie. Augie steals money, plunders store, and defies authorities without any remarkable feeling of remorse afterwards. His adventures in the realm of evil are counterbalanced by his sympathy towards George, optimistic quest for a better fate, enthusiasm for life and his craving for being loved. In this way, the character of Augie is a superb example of masterly craftsmanship of Bellow.

Bellow has made Augie a real genius. Augie shows one the art of living as if he knows what troubles most to a human mind. He is a rebel, a rough, a criminal yet a hero because he has the quality of contentment, which is rare even to a so-called good person. Augie is not polluted by ideologies of society. He does not act to be good but to be true. Augie does not believe in the wisdom of elders because he can easily perceive loopholes in those theories. Therefore, he follows his own discretion.

To be loved and to be admired by others are two basic cravings of human beings. Augie sacrifices these two for his third craving of being free. It is the character of Augie which establishes Bellow as an existentialist in the true sense. Augie is conscious of his status as a free man. That is why he is never a victim of bad faith and remains calm in every situation. Augie is not a winner in any field of life, yet he does not have a burdened conscience. He has nothing to prove. He knows his reality and is content to get rewards accordingly. The story develops Bellow's own views regarding true self and its acceptance. Bellow was himself a rebel whenever it was a question to follow the accepted morality. The conventional morality could never prune Bellow's instinctual drives. Bellow himself could never follow the patterns of behaviour; he should have been followed according to the prescribed codes of conduct.

Bellow is a supporter of truth of human nature. In the true sense, Augie's thoughts present Bellow's own psyche. Augie always supports his instincts and never transfers his guilt to any other person. This is the key to Augie's contentment and Bellow's optimism. Like his creator, Augie is detached; he does not want something particular from his life. If he wants true love, he does not personalize this love within a single person. Rather, he is able to move on knowing the truth that he can get it somewhere else too. In this way he does not attach with any person or object. He is ready to leave and move forward in his quest for another suitable destination, though he never reaches at the same. Even after a chain of disappointment he never loses his hope.

Bellow's novels are a salute to human wish to survive. It is not easy to suffer and similarly one can't avoid suffering. Suffering is universal and perennial. On this earth there are countless human beings who struggle daily. Their minds are thwarted by several kinds of problems—social, familial, individual, psychological etc. Still everybody does not commit suicide. Human beings fight for their existence. Though one's life is unquestionably stuffed with inhuman sufferings, one never loses one's hope to survive. Bellow has always written in appreciation of this hope. This admiration of Bellow is clear when we read the last page of *The Adventures of Augie March*, in which Augie appreciates Jacqueline's wish to lead a hopeful life even after getting assaulted by several intolerable misfortunes.

Bellow's *Augie March* is also peculiar because unlike his other protagonists, Augie does not undergo a change of heart in the end. Augie is not shown to be a prisoner of his own device. He constantly unfolds his future and accepts it as being of his own. Again, Bellow's purpose is fulfilled by Augie's light-hearted acceptance of his struggles and failures. Augie is not tired of his life, instead of that, Jacqueline's hopeful attitude recharges Augie further to live his life with a hope and not as a burden. To say Bellow's vision of human life as sub-angelic may be a little misleading, but Bellow absolutely respects human life for its potential to survive.

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